

Content Marketing – Its Role and Importance as an Emerging Marketing Strategy

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Mrs. K. Victoria Keren Happuch

*Assistant Professor of Commerce
Gonzaga College of Arts and Science for Women
Krishnagiri District*

Abstract

Content marketing is a recent marketing paradigm with creating, sharing, and pulling brand content to the target readers as its focal point (see Steenburgh, Avery & Dahod 2011). However, Pullizi (2010) who coined the term "content marketing," argues that it has been for many years but recently came more to the fore because of succeeding barriers such as more available technologies. This paper is about the study of content marketing and the value it brings to companies. There will be a discussion on the elements and tactics of content marketing that will help a business become successful. And also the current trends in content marketing and steps or stages in content marketing.

Keywords: content marketing, media.

Introduction

"Content purchasing is a strategic brand storytelling technique aimed at changing consumers' inactive behavior within unobtrusive, engaging brand conversations in earned media."

Earned media is accepted for this comment as the conclusion of content marketing depends on the promotion of brand conversations. Irrespective of different viewpoints of what content marketing entails, there is an increasing recognition that it is an innovative pull branding method to create brand awareness, visibility, and trustworthiness in, especially social media. Also, content shopping can drive social media engagement, steer blog or website traffic, or promote a call to action. It can thus be shown that content marketing falls within the marketing information field by pulling the target audience to brand content (Lieb 2012 & Miller 2013). When a pull strategy is adopted, consumers who are already interested in the brand or are seeking information or advice, are attracted to brand content because of its relevancy (Holliman & Rowley 2014).

Brand content often takes the form of brand stories strategically linked to the company's brand personality or brand persona to catch the attention of customers based on relevancy to their own lives. These brand stories are then shared on social media or via email support using search engine optimized (SEO) blog posts, free eBooks, infographics, videos, whitepapers, podcasts, webinars, press

releases, case studies, testimonials, and interviews, to name but a few. That is typically done to encourage electronic word of mouth (eWOM), social media engagement, or converting the purpose readers into long-term loyal customers (see Pulizzi 2010; 2012 & 2014).

What is Content Marketing?

Content marketing is a content-based marketing strategy focused on content creation (textual and visual) and the distribution of those content using different channels. Though the basic motive is conversion, the marketing approach should not be promotional. Your content should help grow interested in your products or services amongst the target audience.

Content Marketing is one of the most powerful SEO (Search Engine Optimised) services that a business can practice to popularize its products or services and to achieve a higher organic position on the search engines such as Google or Bing. It is an advanced and a mixed approach of SEO and content creation. Thus, adopting a content marketing strategy is a way forward, towards establishing a digital presence that attracts the attention and the imagination of your users.

Research Methodology

Data used in this study is secondary and is taken from various sources such as journals, periodicals, articles, books, reports, websites, etc.

Content Marketing Trends for 2019

Content Marketing has grown one of the most comprehensive digital marketing strategies for all small-to-medium and medium-to-large organizations and enterprises. Businesses tend to look for trends in their marketing activities. With the expansion of digital marketing and continuous adoption of new facets of online marketing, companies now have protocols in place to keep pace with the rapid transformations. Every business wants to be a part of the digital marketing evolution, and they are either participating or are waiting in the wings to join the digital revolution.

The main chunk of digital marketing is directly dependent on content marketing. The growth of content marketing is placed, and a research report of Statista validates it. Content marketing revenue generation worldwide in 2014 was 144.81 billion USD. It is also prophesied that the content marketing revenue generation worldwide in 2019 will be 313.42 billion USD. A steep growth of around 168.61 billion USD within five years, is one of the major reasons for businesses wanting to be a part of this growth. It is clear that many companies willingly accept newer trends and marketing strategies to ensure their successes.

Content Purchasing Tactics

Content can be present in a variety of formats including blogs, infographics, slide decks, case studies, white papers, e-books, videos, quizzes, memes, and images, etc. B2C marketers are increasing the number of tactics used each year. The most widely used content marketing tactics by B2C companies were articles on the company website, social media, blogs, eNewsletters, and videos. However, the tactics believe to be more efficient are not those most generally used by B2C marketers, for example, videos are believed to be more powerful than social media, but marketers use this tactic less.

1. Videos and Tutorials

Videos may be entertaining or informative, focusing on a specific topic related to the product or service. This content tactic can range from tutorials, testimonials, presentations, vlogs, case studies, etc. (Jefferson & Tanton, 2013). Tutorials are which that teaches customers something new in a way that is easy to understand, using step-by-step instructions.

YouTube, the video-sharing website, is the second search platform after Google. Of all the content that is included in Google's general search listings, the video develops the most frequently, considering 70% of the search results (Searchmetrics). Notably, video content is more likely to place a website on the first page of a search engine. Internet users tend to spend, on average, two more times on websites when they contain videos. Consumers are switching to video for demonstrations and product reviews when making purchase decisions. More than 3 out of 5 consumers will spend at least 2 minutes watching a video that educates them about a product or service they are planning to obtain (Marketingcharts.com, 2012).

The video was the second most popular type of content used across channels. The importance of a video is dependent on the audience that it is trying to reach and the actual nature and content of the video. It is not a suitable medium for all targets.

2. User-generated content (UGC)

UGC refers to knowledge and material that is produced and posted by Internet users (Lanchester, 2006). User-generated content can be individually or collaboratively created, shared, consumed, and modified (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). It has many forms in common media, from Facebook posts, Twitter tweets, to consumer-produced reviews and advertisements, etc. (Smith et al., 2012). Customers mainly rely on UGC to purchase decision-making (Riegner, 2007; MacKinnon, 2012).

Users trust UGC more producer-generated content (Cheong & Morrison, 2008; MacKinnon, 2012), which is that designed and shared by the brands, as they think other users will share both positive and negative product expertise with the purpose of full disclosure and perceived non-commercial interest, which makes them unbiased evaluators of a product's or service's qualities. Consumers produce UGC when sharing their activities and views of products and services.

3. Electronic Word of Sound (EWOM)

EWOM is generated when customers generate their knowledge on the Internet. eWOM is "any positive or contradictory statement made by actual, potential, or former customers about a product or company, which is made accessible to several people and businesses via the Internet" (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004, p.39). It consists of emails, forums, social networks, reviews, chats, and blogs (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004). It is supposed to be a powerful form of information since it is regarded as highly reliable and trustworthy (Godes & Mayzlin, 2004). Whether the negative or positive room has a great influence on consumer behavior (Chevalier & Mayzlin, 2006), forming consumers' purchase intention (Zhang & Tran, 2009), and affecting purchase behavior (Reigner, 2007).

4. Social Media

Social media is a "group of internet-based relationships that build on the technological and ideological and support of Web 2.0, which allows the creation and exchange for UGC" (Kaplan & Haelnein, 2010, p.61). The content created by social media users is usually defined as UGC or consumer-generated media (CGM) (Gretzel & Xiang, 2010). Social media covers various "new sources of online learning that are received, designed, circulated and used by consumers intent on teaching each other about brands, products, settings, personalities and issues" (Nazzaro & Blackshaw, 2004, p.2). Users of social media projects are not only consumers but also generators and donors of such content (Levina & Arrigara, 2008). Social media has become a great source of material for all market partners. It is currently one of the most important and most reliable experts of knowledge for enterprises and consumers. (World Internet Project, 2013).

5. Customer Reviews

Consumers publicize their evaluations of a commodity or service performance through consumer reviews (Chen et al., 2003). eWOM plays a significant role in influencing buying behavior. Customer reviews are more relevant for this task than expert reviews. People will write positive or rejecting articles depending on the emotional incentive. When developing positive WOM, one perceives gains of social approval or self-approval by displaying their big purchase decision. A customer who shares negative consumer reviews is usually one seeking vengeance. More than 70% of consumers will consult reports and ratings before purchase, and agree that reviews make them more comfortable that they are the right commodity or service. Moreover, 63% of customers are more likely to buy from a site if it contains product reviews.

6. Quality of Content

Online purchasing differs from popular shopping in many ways, such as the disability to physically inspect product condition before purchase (Jarvenpaa & Todd, 1997). The digital consumer must, consequently, rely on the quality of the information accessible to them online to infer on the nature of the product they are looking to acquire, before making the online transaction. Learning quality refers to a consumer’s perception of the quality of the information presented on a website. Group consists of two dimensions: the application of content and completeness of the knowledge (Yang et al., 2005; Ko & Hur, 2005). Fitness refers to the relevance, accuracy, benefit, and timeliness of the information provided. A consumer’s perceptions of the usefulness of an informational environment are strongly related to the quality of the knowledge (Kellers et al., 2013). Completeness refers to whether the information is perceived to be comprehensive and complete (Liu et al., 2000).

7. Quantity of Content

Learning quantity refers to the number of items or attributes used in describing an alternative (e.g., brand, product) (Wilkie, 1974; Summers, 1974). Processing additional information has both benefits and costs. Knowledge overload has complimentary results on customer helps consumers and satisfaction levels feel less involved about selection; nonetheless, too much information contributes to reduced quality of consumer purchase decision (Jacoby et al., 1974). It generally becomes hard for consumers to identify items that are surely relevant when there is an improvement in information, resulting in higher search costs for the customer (Klapp, 1986). Nevertheless, the level of customer satisfaction grows proportionately with the abundance of knowledge, even if it is perceived that there is a loss of efficiency in the decision-making process (Jacoby et al., 1974).

8. Postures

Attitudes are a “summary construct that describes an individual’s overall feelings toward or evaluation of an object” (Belch & Belch, 2003, p.117). Attitudes are composed of three dimensions: affective, cognitive, and behavioral intent. Nature has been proposed to influence behavioral intentions (Davis, 1989), which are followed by actual behavior (Scheffold et al., 2001).

In the Internet context, nature is an overall evaluation of the transaction activities with a web retailer. A favorable approach is expected to reduce barriers to the adoption of e-commerce and actual transaction and facilitate online transaction intentions. (Pavlou et al., 2002).

The content marketing tactic chosen becomes necessary since the message source that customers recognize as most likely will have a strong positive impact on their approach towards the message (Friedman & Friedman, 1979).

9. Purchase Purposes

Intention to purchase is the possibility that a potential customer will buy from a commerce website for the first time, and purpose of continued investment is the possibility that the online shopper will return to the website and obtain again in the future (Davis, 1998). It can also be described as a consumer's aim to engage in an electronic exchange relationship with a web retailer, such as sharing knowledge, conducting transactions, and maintaining a relationship (Zwass, 1998). Purchase intention is a step in the decision-making method where a shopper studies the reasons to buy a specific product (Shah et al., 2012). At this critical point, consumers access and evaluate the particular product, to determine whether to purchase and in what conditions.

Many customers, who search for websites to purchase, subsequently abandon their purchase due to the low quality of the websites (Boston Consulting Group 2000; Forrester Research, 1999). Since a company's e-commerce website is the spokesperson of the company's online presence, low website quality will reflect poorly on the company, weakening customer intention to go shopping or return to the website (Nielsen, 2000). Since the higher, the higher the consumer's intent to shop online, the website quality, a website of character device can push the Customer to a prosperous transaction and attract them to attend the website again (Li & Zhang, 2002).

Content Marketing Process Model

Content marketing process model 2PDM (Planning, Production, Distribute and Communicate, Measurement also Optimization) is displayed below:

1. Planning (P): makes the first step of a content marketing process model. This stage involves three steps: "designation business objectives from content marketing," "designation target audiences," and "creating an editorial calendar." The editorial calendar for content editing is a timeline that specifies the frequency of content publishing and content distribution channels. The planning stage is a rotating process. That means that there are three steps from the planning stage of the back and forth route for adjusting the levels.

2. Production (P): The second stage of the content marketing process model refers to content creation; at this stage, the content related to the intentions and concerns of target audiences will be satisfied. In this regard, it is essential to pay attention to the inherent elements in the production of content and content elements. Content essential elements include all factors that help marketers generate valuable content. The most important of these are value, relevance, reliability, sharing, entertainment, exclusive, coherence, and purposeful content. Additionally, at this stage, the marketer must get at the form of the material produced in terms of the prevalence of the format and its use with a variety of tools and platforms for its users and the ability to share it. That is, the content should not only be in proportion to the distribution media, in terms of volume and duration, but also in a way that can be easily shared with the audience and allows the public to use it simultaneously.

3. Distribution (D): At this stage, the marketer should choose a media that is highly interactive and capable of being widely used between customers based on the type of content. It is more critical at this stage to determine the type of content distribution strategy (pull/push/ or both).

4. Measurement (M): At this stage, content marketing experiences and activities are evaluated using the main dimensions (consumption, share, lead generation and sales), and the results obtained from this stage for making decisions and planning are used to efficiently complete of content shopping.

Conclusion

Brands will now accomplish their shopping goals, not mainly through interruptive media, but by creating and sharing the most valuable information on the planet for that particular niche.

Content marketing was excited a considerable time ago. However, not many companies interested in it back then. Nevertheless, it is growing the new trend in the marketing world lately due to the shift in customer management and technological aspects. Customers realize the potential of knowledge and information can lead to better purchasing decisions. Thus they start to demand more knowledge. Moreover, they are smarter and getting smarter, so marketers have no choice but to produce accurate and high contents because manipulation of information does not work in this digital age.

References

1. Content Marketing World looks at the importance of linguistics in brand strategy. (2014). MultiLingual, 25(8), 6.
2. Fuller, J. (2010). Refining Virtual Co-Creation from a Consumer Perspective. California Management Review, 52(2), 98-122. DOI: 10.1525/cm.2010.52.2.98.
3. “The Review of Content Marketing as a New Trend in Marketing Practices,” International Journal of Management, Accounting, and Economics Vol. 2, No. 9, September 2015
4. Academic guidelines for content marketing: research-based recommendations for better practice.
5. Cole, J.T., & Greer, J.D. (2013). Audience Response to Brand Journalism: The Effect of Frame, Source, and Involvement. Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly, 90(4), 673-690. Doi: 10.1177/1077699013503160.
6. Content Marketing vs. Traditional Marketing | Newsocial. (2013, July 6).New social. Retrieved March 20, 2014, from <http://www.newsocial.com/content-marketing-vs-traditionalmarketing/>
7. New research shows an increasing reliance on content marketing to drive brand awareness, inbound traffic, and sales. (2013, Oct 01).Business Wire. <http://ezproxy.lib.calpoly.edu/login?url=http://search.proquest.com/docview/1437739586?accountid=10362> Park, Content Marketing Institute (2014), “B2C Content Marketing 2014 Benchmarks, Budgets and Trends – North America”, report.